

Reconstruction of prestin ancestors sheds light on the evolution of its area-motor activity

Nicolas Fuentes-Ugarte,^{1, a)} Tiaren Ruiz-Rojas,^{2, a)} Victor Castro-Fernandez,^{1, b)}
and Raul Araya-Secchi^{2, 3, c)}

¹*Departamento de Biología, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Chile, Santiago, Chile.*

²*Computational Biophysics Group, Facultad de Ingeniería, Tecnología y Diseño, Universidad San Sebastian, Santiago, Chile.*

³*Centro Basal Ciencia & Vida, Universidad San Sebastian, Santiago, Chile.*

^{a)}These authors contributed equally to this work

^{b)}Corresponding author: vcasfe@uchile.cl

^{c)}Corresponding author: raul.araya@uss.cl

Abstract The mammalian hearing organ shows high sensitivity and frequency selectivity. One of the key processes responsible for these features is the mechanical amplification of sound carried out by the outer hair cells (OHCs) of the inner ear through electromotility (EM). Electromotility is driven by prestin, a membrane protein member of the SLC26 family of transporters that acts as a voltage-dependent area motor. Strikingly, prestin only plays this role in mammals whereas in non-mammals, it acts as an anion transporter without significant piezoelectric activity. Studies aimed at explaining the origin of these differences found at least three regions of interest located in the transmembrane domain (TMD). However, to date, the effect of these differences on prestin function has not been placed in the context of its structure and dynamics. Furthermore, a region of high variability among members of the SCL26 family has been practically overlooked: The the intervening sequence (IVS) on the Sulphate Transporter and AntiSigma factor antagonist (STAS) domain. In this study, we combined phylogenetic analysis, reconstruction of ancestral prestin sequences, and structural modeling to offer a comparative analysis of prestin evolution from a structural point of view and to shed light on how its unique sequence features may play a role in the generation and tuning of EM. Our results suggest that sequence/structural differences in the TMD are related to changes in the interactions within the protein domains and between the protein and lipids leading to a gradual reduction of its ion transport capability while enhancing its voltage sensitivity essential for electromotility. Regarding the IVS, our results suggest that, in placental mammals, a unique patch of negative residues may directly interact with residues that form the entrance of the intracellular cavity of the adjacent monomer and modulate the response to voltage or frequency changes.

INTRODUCTION

Electromotility (EM) in the outer hair cells (OHCs) is essential for the amplification of sound in the mammalian inner ear, a key factor associated to the extraordinary sensitivity and frequency selectivity of mammalian hearing [1, 2, 3, 4]. EM is driven by prestin, a unique membrane protein from the SLC26 family (SLC26A5) that operates as a voltage-dependent area-motor [5, 6, 7]. Phylogenetic analyses have revealed that mammalian prestin evolved from an anion transporter present in a pre-mammalian ancestor [8, 9, 10]. However, mammalian prestin does not function as an ion transporter, unlike its non-mammalian orthologs, which can exchange divalent chloride anions [11, 12]. Research has shown that mammalian and non-mammalian prestin orthologs exhibit nonlinear capacitance (NLC) with inverse relationship between anion transport and motor function [9, 12]. However, the specifics of how prestin motor function evolved, including its specialization and fine-tuning in placental mammalian remain unresolved, despite the identification of critical residues and regions [13, 14, 15].

To shed light on the structural aspect of this evolutionary process, we employed ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) and structural modeling to identify key substitutions in prestin evolution and place them in a structural context by mapping them to prestin domains and regions (TMD, STAS, IVS, EC-loop). Our goal is to enhance the understanding of the adaptations of prestin in mammals and their implications for auditory function. This approach not only highlights known functional areas but also focuses on those that have remained unexplored, particularly on the intervening sequence (IVS) on prestin STAS domain.

RESULTS

We started by generating a phylogenetic tree for the Chordate SLC26A5 subfamily (Fig. 1A), and identified five monophyletic groups corresponding to fish, amphibians, reptiles, birds, and mammals with a topology consistent with previously reported phylogenetic relationships [16, 17]. We deduced the most probable sequence of 12 ancestors in the Chordata prestin phylogeny by ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) [18] (Fig. 1A). The inferred sequences, listed in Table 1, have a mean posterior probability per residue higher than 0.95 indicating a high robustness. Our sequence analysis focused on the evolutionary pathway from fish to placental mammals (ancPis → ancRhi → ancTre → ancAmn → ancMam → ancThe → ancPla) using as initial reference (outgroup) the closest homologous transporter, human SLC26A6 (HsA6), and human SLC26A5 (HsPres) as a model of current placental mammal prestin. This analysis identified 149 substitutions (83 in the TMD and 66 in the STAS domain), categorized into: (1) **early substitutions** (n = 82) occurring in the **ancAmn** → **ancMam** transition, (2) **intermediate substitutions** (n = 17), in the **ancMam** → **ancThe** transition and (3) **late substitutions** (n = 17), from the **ancThe** → **ancPla** transition. We also found substitutions that occur in two and three steps during the evolutionary trajectory, an indicator of higher variability in these positions.

Figure 1: ancestral sequence reconstruction of SLC26A5 members (A) Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of prestin protein (SLC26A5) from Chordata. The JTT+G+I model was used for phylogenetic and ancestral sequences reconstruction. Sequences colored as follow: Dark cyan Pisces, dark magenta Amphibian, green Reptilian, red Birds, light blue monotremata mammals, navy blue marsupialia mammals and bright navy blue placentalia mammals. The extant sequences of *Homo sapiens*, *Meriones unguiculatus* and *Tursiops truncatus* are highlighted with their respective PDB accession codes. Circles indicate nodes where ancestral sequences were inferred in this study. (B) Mapping of substitutions on human prestin topology. Early, green squares; intermediate yellow triangles; late, orange circles; two-step, blue X; three step, gray X. Non-conservative substitutions red stars.

Table 1: Robustness of the Ancestral Sequence Reconstructions.

Ancestor	Description	Node Support	ASR Mean Posterior probability \pm SD
ancPis	Last common ancestor from Pisces	99.98%	0.974 \pm 0.092
ancRhi	Last common ancestor from Rhipidistia	96.68%	0.972 \pm 0.095
ancTre	Last common ancestor from Tetrapoda	99.98%	0.952 \pm 0.125
ancAmp	Last common ancestor from Amphibia	77.94%	0.973 \pm 0.090
ancAmn	Last common ancestor from Amniota	99.98%	0.974 \pm 0.088
ancRep	Last common ancestor from Reptilia	93.41%	0.977 \pm 0.083
ancArch	Last common ancestor from Archosauria	99.98%	0.978 \pm 0.081
ancAvi	Last common ancestor from Avis	99.98%	0.976 \pm 0.084
ancMam	Last common ancestor from Mammalia	99.98%	0.959 \pm 0.108
ancThe	Last common ancestor from Theria	99.98%	0.962 \pm 0.113
ancMar	Last common ancestor from Marsupialia	99.98%	0.996 \pm 0.033
ancPla	Last common ancestor from Placentalia	99.98%	0.999 \pm 0.001

Regarding the nature of the substitution, 41% (n = 61) are conservative hydrophobic substitutions, 41% (n = 61) change polarity, and 18% (n = 27) involve charged residues. Substitutions that present major differences in their properties, i.e non-conservative substitutions (presented in **bold*** throughout the text), represented 48% (n = 39) of early substitutions, 29% (n = 5) of intermediate substitutions, and 71% of late substitutions (n = 12), suggesting that the specific functional properties of placental mammalian prestin may be based on some of these 12 substitutions.

Mapping the substitutions, on the topology of human prestin (Fig. 1B), we observed that early substitutions are

distributed throughout the TMD and STAS domains. Remarkably, a concentration of non-conservative early substitutions are observed in TM5b-TM6, EC-loop and STAS domain. For the intermediate substitutions, they are mapped mainly to TM5b- TM6 and the STAS domain. Late substitutions, are found between TM3, EC-loop to TM8 and mainly in the STAS domain.

Comparison of structural models of reconstructed prestin ancestors

To place the substitutions in a structural context, we generated structural predictions for ancestral prestins using AF2-multimer (V3) [19, 20] (Fig. 2). The models resemble an expanded state similar to the sensor-down II dolphin prestin structure [15] (PDB-ID: 7S9C) with an RMSD-C α of 3.3 Å and 4.8 Å with the structure of human prestin in the presence of NaCl [21] (PDB-ID: 7LGU). All the models showed high structural similarity in the TMD, with slight variability in the EC-loop and TM6-TM7 loop. In the STAS domain, the IVS adopted distinct conformations between the models: The non-mammalian ancestors show a longer C α 2 helix (Fig. 2A-D) whereas the mammalian ancestors and hsPres, show either a shorter C α 2 helix and a longer disordered loop (ancMam, ancThe) (Fig. 2E-F) or a broken helix (C α 2 + C α 2') that brings the IVS-loop towards the extracellular entrance (EC-entrance) of the adjacent monomer (ancPla, human) (Fig. 2G-H).

Figure 2: Reconstruction of ancestral prestin structures using AF2-multimer(V3). Models for ancPis (A), ancRhi (B), ancTre (C), ancAmn (D), ancMam (E), ancThe (F), ancPla (G) and human prestin (H) are shown in cartoon representation colored by confidence (pLDDT).

Structural analysis of the substitutions found in the transmembrane domain

Mapping the substitutions found on the TMD into our models shows that early and intermediate substitutions are located both near and far from the chloride-binding site, while late substitutions are distant. This suggests that early changes contributed to the loss of ion transport and the emergence of EM, whereas late substitutions optimized and fine-tuned this mechanism to provide the high sensitivity and selectivity observed in placental mammals [10].

We divided our analysis of these substitutions into four groups:

(1) Residues 86-140 (numbering according to human prestin) from TM1 and TM2, and residues 381-438 from TM9 to TM11 were shown to be key to generate mammalian-like NLC and EM in non-mammalian prestin [13]. In our models, these regions form the "core" of the so called transport domain (also known as core domain, see 1B) with an extensive contact interface. Several early and intermediate substitutions can be found in these regions: For example, M93L and Y101F (early) and **T136P*** (intermediate) that when mutated completely abolished NLC [13]. Other substitutions found here are: F121I (early) and **T124C*** (early); V384I (early), S405G (early), **T415C*** (early), **S417A*** (early), I419L (early), V421I (early), V426L (early), **I428T*** (early), Y430F (early), **T438A*** (early) and **F387L*** (intermediate). Several of these substitutions point their sidechains towards the lipids with some notable exceptions in the C-terminal ends of TM2 and TM11: Ile212 (TM2) interacts with Leu419 (TM11) and more importantly Cys124

(TM2) with Cys415 (TM11), positioned close enough to form a disulfide bond that could have appeared in the therian (ancThe) ancestor (Fig. 3A) and could restrict or couple the movement of these two helices. The effect of mutations on these non-conserved cysteines has been highlighted albeit without a structural context [22]. To our knowledge, this is the first time that the potential formation of this disulfide bond on mammalian prestin is reported or explicitly mentioned, as it has not been addressed on the publications associated to deposited prestin structures. The combination of these substitutions in the transport domain, could explain the transition to an enhanced EM prestin that can still perform transport as attested by a synthetic prestin produced in [13] that showed both functions.

(2) The EC-loop [14]. Here we found early and late substitutions that result in different conformation and orientation of the loop between non-mammal and mammal ancestors. In non-mammal ancestors, the loop faces the extracellular surface of its monomer (ancAmn on Fig. 3B), facilitating the formation of interactions with residues from TM4, TM5-TM5b loop and TM5b. Whereas in mammal ancestors, the loop points outwards decoupling TM3 and the loop from other regions (Fig. 3B). Overall, substitutions in this region decrease both the negative charges surrounding the putative EC-entrance to prestin and appear to decouple TM3 from other parts of the extracellular side.

(3) TM6. The flexibility of this helix has been suggested to play a role on NLC/EM due to the accumulation of intra-helix glycines in mammalian prestin [15]. Of the glycines found on ancPla (and hPres), two correspond to early substitutions **V270G***, **S274G***, and one to a late substitution **V263G***. Furthermore, we found several substitutions in TM6 that could be relevant for its flexibility: Four early substitutions **A261S***, **I269F**, **I278F** and **D280E**; two intermediate substitutions **A260C***, **I267M**, and one late substitution **C268V***. Creating a pattern where the N-terminal half of TM6 contains intermediate and late substitutions, while the C-terminal half contains early substitutions. These intermediate and late substitutions participate in interactions with TM7 and TM12 (Fig. 3C-D) and could cause restriction to the rotation or displacement of TM6. Additionally, early substitutions in TM6 and TM12 perturb an electrostatic contact network between these helices due to the **D280E** substitution on TM6, and the **K543M*** substitution on TM12 (Fig. 3C-D) which would reduce the strength of the interaction between both helices. Residues that are part of this network, Lys276, Glu280, and Lys449 in mammalian prestin, have been shown to affect NLC/EM when mutated to Gln [23], which highlights the role of the TM6 - TM12 interaction on prestin function. Taken together, a more flexible TM6 appeared during the ancAmn → ancMam transition followed by intermediate and late substitutions that modify interactions with TM7 and TM12 to control the movement of the more flexible C-terminal half of mammalian TM6.

(4) Finally, we highlight a set of non-conservative early substitutions in TM13 that result in a unique pattern only found in mammalian prestin: Substitutions **V470T***, **V474T*** and **A478S*** enhance the polarity of the external face of TM13 which could lead to alterations in membrane fluidity or thickness in the inter-monomer space. In TM14 we mapped early substitutions **L489I**, **A493I** and **M496L*** that could alter the dimer interface. Overall these substitutions could affect the lipid environment on the inter-monomer space, and are perhaps related to the membrane deformation reported by [21] and to the evolutionary changes associated with prestin sensitivity to membrane thickness [24] (Fig. 4).

Figure 3: Substitutions in the TMD. (A) Substitutions in TM1-2 and TM9-11. Protein shown as ribbons with the scaffold and transport domains colored as in Fig. 1B. Substitutions shown in VdW representation. Only the TMD of one monomer is shown for clarity. (B) Substitutions in the EC-loop. (C-D) Substitutions in TM6 in the ancAmn (C) and ancPla (D) models. The scaffold domain is shown as ribbons and the transport domain as surface colored as in A. In all panels substitutions colored as in 1B. Non-conservative substitutions marked with a *.

Figure 4: Substitutions found on TM13-14. (A-B) Surface representation with the transport domain colored as in Fig. 3C and the scaffold domain colored by residue type (hydrophobic = white, polar = green, acidic = red, basic = blue). (A) ancMam (B) ancPla.

Structural analysis of the substitutions found in the STAS domain

Figure 5: Detail of the unique features of ancPla IVS. (A) Superposition of a monomer of the ancPla model (colored by pLDDT as in Fig. 2) onto the structure of human prestin 7LGU [21] (grey) shown in cartoon representation. (B-C) Electrostatic potential maps of ancPla (B) and ancAmn (C).

The most notable structural difference between the predicted structures of non-mammalian and mammalian ancestors lies on the IVS in the STAS domain (Fig. 2). Several early, late and two-step substitutions accumulate here (see Fig. 1B). In our models, we observed that mammalian ancestors (ancThe onwards) present the non-conservative substitution **K583G*** breaking helix $C\alpha 2$ into two helical segments: $C\alpha 2$ and $C\alpha 2'$ (Fig. 2(G-H)) that result in positioning the IVS-loop close to the entrance of the intracellular cavity (IC-cavity) of the adjacent monomer. This feature is more pronounced in the placental ancestor (ancPla) (see Fig. 5A) and hsPres perhaps due to substitutions in positions 584, 585 and 587 which result in the NANMANA motif that has a higher helix propensity. After $C\alpha 2'$ we find Pro607 (two-step) and more notably, three two-step substitutions that increase the number of negatively charged residues on the IVS-loop creating a negative patch (NP) (Glu609, Glu610, and Asp611). The NP is placed near the entrance of the IC-cavity of the adjacent monomer (Fig. 5B-C) and could interact with positively charged residues on the IC side of the TMD. Charge reversal mutations of this NP showed a slight shift on NLC [25] suggesting an indirect role in EM/NLC tuning. The negative patch is followed by a series of two and three-step substitutions that result in the PPIVKSTF motif, unique for placental mammals, involved in contacts that stabilize the inward-looking IVS-loop. Thus, changes that lead to the formation of $C\alpha 2'$ and the negative patch are accompanied by changes in other regions of the STAS domain that could stabilize this new conformation.

The IVS has been predicted to be disordered so we need to look at structural ensembles to make useful inferences. To achieve this, we enhanced the conformational sampling of AF2-multimer(V3) by using multiple seeds and the *dropout* option (see Methods). This resulted in the generation of 1280 predictions for each sequence that explored the flexibility of the IVS-loop and other flexible regions, with minor variation observed in the TMD (see Fig. 6A-D). For the mammalian models, particularly ancPla and hsPres, the IVS loop is predicted in conformations that appear to be moving in and out of the entrance of the IC-cavity of the adjacent monomer facilitated by the aforementioned break in helix $C\alpha 2$. Conversely, the non-mammalian ancestors, show an extended helical region that places the flexible part of the loop far from the adjacent IC-entrance. To quantify these observations, we measured the distance between the center of mass (COM) of the IVS-loop of one monomer and the chloride-binding site of the adjacent monomer. The distribution of distances is shown in Fig. 6E. In this plot a bimodal distribution is observed for human prestin (hsPres) and the placental ancestor (ancPla), suggesting the existence of two states where the IVS-loop is close or far from the adjacent chloride-binding site.

Figure 6: Conformational sampling of the IVS(A-D) Representative conformations obtained for human and ancestral prestin models. Only one monomer of the models is shown and the other correspond to the human prestin structure 7LGU [21] shown as a gray surface. (E) Distribution of the distance between the center of mass of the IVS-loop of one monomer and the chloride-binding site of the adjacent monomer.

DISCUSSION

The evolutionary trajectory of prestin reveals transitions that facilitated its divergence from an anion transporter in non-mammals to a voltage-dependent motor protein in mammals. Using ancestral sequence reconstruction, our study identified key amino acid substitutions in the TMD and STAS domains that underpin this shift. Notably, early substitutions during the amniote to mammalian transition appear to have modified the interactions within the protein and between the protein and lipids leading to a gradual reduction of its ion transport capability while enhancing its voltage sensitivity essential for electromotility. Intermediate and late substitutions may have provided the fine-tuning necessary to provide the precise frequency selectivity characteristic of mammalian hearing.

Structural modeling offers additional insights, particularly regarding the IVS region in the STAS domain. In placental mammals, the presence of a unique patch of negatively charged residues positioned near the intracellular cavity of the adjacent monomer, suggest that this region could play a role in the voltage response. These findings underscore specific evolutionary changes that refined the function of prestin, contributing to cochlear amplification and the precise frequency selectivity characteristics of mammalian hearing.

METHODS

Multiple sequence alignment, phylogenetic inference, and ancestral sequence reconstruction

Eukaryotic SLC26 structural models were retrieved from the AF2-EBI database [26] and aligned using STAMP [27]. Refinement of the N-terminal and C-terminal segments was carried out using ClustalW [28]. For the multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of chordate prestin, sequences were retrieved from the non-redundant protein database (nr) using BLASTp, with the HsPres (PDB-ID: 7GLU) as the template. Sequences exhibiting over 98% identity were filtered out via CD-HIT [29], while those with lengths higher than 870 and lower than 570 residues were excluded. The resulting set of sequences (n=248) was aligned with the structural profile derived from CryoEM structures of HsPres (PDB-ID: 7GLU), TtPres (PDB-ID: 7S8X), and MuPres (PDB-ID: 7SUN) using ClustalW and STAMP. Evolutionary models were selected using SMS2.0 [30], followed by the inference of maximum-likelihood (ML) phylogenetic trees using PhyML [31]. Ancestral sequences were inferred using the empirical Bayes method with PAML 4.4 [32], employing the Lazarus tool as described by Handson-Smith [33]. Probability calculations for each amino acid at each alignment position for each target node were calculated, selecting the amino acids with the highest probabilities. Gap positions were inferred via ML, using the discrete characters model in Mesquite [34] as previously reported [35].

Generation of structural models

Dimeric, full-length structural predictions of the reconstructed ancestral prestin sequences and HsPres were generated using AlphaFold2-multimer (V3) [19, 20] within the colabfold-batch 1.5.5 implementation [36]. No templates were used in this process.

Conformational sampling

We enhanced the conformational sampling of AlphaFold2-multimer (V3) using multiple seeds and the *dropout* option that introduces epistemic uncertainty and leads to a broader exploration of potential structures by the model [37].

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Online Forum]

[Haosheng Wen and Marcos Sotomayor] AF3 is here. Have you compared the similarities and differences (if any) between AF3 and AF2 models of prestin proteins across different species/ancestral reconstructions? It would be interesting to check, especially for positions of key amino acid substitutions identified in your analyses.

[Raul Araya-Secchi] We have compared the predictions AF3 and the models look essentially the same. Furthermore, there seems to be an issue with AF3 that tries to impose alpha-helical structure onto disordered regions thus the IVS less disordered. Also, since we cannot do the conformational sampling with AF3 yet, we rather stay with AF2 for the moment.

[Haosheng Wen and Marcos Sotomayor] The Cys124-Cys415 disulfide bond is highlighted and the text implies that is absent in the structures. Is this correct? Is it because those regions were not in the structures? Wouldn't that argue against it?

[Raul Araya-Secchi] We do not imply that the Cys124-Cys415 disulfide bond is absent in the deposited structures. Rather, we highlight that its potential existence has not been explicitly addressed. Examination of the deposited prestin structures indicates that these two residues are indeed close enough to form an S-S bond. However, the associated publications do not discuss the formation of this bond. Additionally, no other studies have confirmed the presence of this disulfide bond, likely because previous research on prestin cysteines was conducted before the structural data were available, which revealed the proximity of these two cysteines. Thus, we think that it is worthy to experimentally assess the presence of such bond and ascertain its relevance for EM/NL.

[Haosheng Wen and Marcos Sotomayor] Can you suggest mutations, based on your analyses, that would convert prestin back into a transporter? Can you do the opposite? (take an SLC26 transporter and transform it into an area motor).

[Raul Araya-Secchi] This is a very interesting question and it has in part been already answered in works such as [13] and [14]. However, I believe that our work provides further residues and regions whose relevance for NLC/EM and or transport functions has to be evaluated. For example, residues on TM6 other than the glycines, or pair of residues that form interactions between TM6 and TM12 and that show differences between mammalian and non-mammalians. Or, the polar on TM13 and the negative patch on the IVS found only on mammalian ancestors. It is difficult to predict what would happen if these residues are mutated or exchanged, but they certainly should be tested to determine their role in prestin function and whether their presence only in mammalian prestin is related to the area-motor function

and/or voltage-sensing.

[Haosheng Wen and Marcos Sotomayor] One figure clearly depicting each domain of prestin will help readers who are not experts on prestin understand the content better.

[Raul Araya-Secchi] Thanks for the suggestion. We have included labeling of all the domains on panel A of Figure 2.

[Post-Talk Q & A]

[Paul Secchia] I thought that talk was extremely interesting and cool. I had a question about, whether or not with the, the longer IVS-loop that we saw in the ancestral amniotes, if another potential cause of its ability to move in and out is that you might be able to pack more of the mammalian prestin and like if it's smaller in space, so you could fit more of them into a given area, and if that might have any effect.

[Raul Araya-Secchi] That's actually a pretty interesting question. I haven't thought about that. But maybe you're right, and there are some studies where they did simulations of multiple prestin molecules, and they kind of ordered together, so maybe it can help them pack closer. Yes, there's also evidence that the region before the loop, can be helpful for binding to other proteins, but, the packing is a very interesting question. We'll sure try to look into that. Thank you.

[Kuni Iwasa] I'm interested in the thickness dependence of prestin molecules. I mean, we have seen thickness dependence in mammalian prestin well as avian.

[Raul Araya-Secchi] Yeah. We think that this polar patch that we found in the inter monomer region of the mammalian ancestors could change how prestin reacts to thickness or changes in the thickness of the membrane. That's why I was very sad that, Navid Bavi was not here because he was going to talk about, prestin lipid interactions. So maybe he could have had more insight into how the lipid environment affects prestin function or the other way around and how this polar patch can do something.

[Robert Raphael] It's a little bit of a follow up. So, many years ago we proposed that the electric field could induce a curvature change in prestin and your residues there on the inner surface may give us a mechanistic explanation for that if those are inside and not outside the electric field will then induce a curvature. So can you look at the membrane profile and make some simplifying assumptions.

[Raul Araya-Secchi] Once we run simulations of our models in the presence of lipids, we definitely want to check what's going on there in terms of curvature or thickness. And, of course we should at some point include cholesterol because we know that cholesterol can also modulate the function of prestin. So definitely now that we have these models, we have a lot of other stuff to do to, to try to figure out if these substitutions that we found are relevant or not for function.

[Robert Fettiplace] I don't know whether you're aware, but we showed that in fact, prestin was operational in chicken short hair cells. And, I think the evidence was reasonably good, but recently I found that in fact it's also present in the short hair cells. So in fact, the functional part of the prestin must have evolved with the archosaurs.

[Raul Araya-Secchi] I was hoping for your question because I have had the chicken in my mind throughout this whole study. And maybe what happened is that perhaps the capacity of prestin to act as a motor is an older thing, not a newer innovation, right? It's not a mammalian innovation and maybe what we see from mammalian onward are just the fine tuning that mammals require for their highly sensitive hearing. So, we definitely want to give a more a more detailed look into that and so far we have been a bit mammalian centric in our vision. So we want to expand our look and see whether we can say something like the motor activity is earlier and then it was just fine tuned.